

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ALI****FIRST NAME: SARA****PROGRAM CODE: Type PROGRAM CODE****COURSE CODE : ACA 401 D****PERIOD NUMBER: PERIOD 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 6%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2010 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Basics of Academic Essay (EUCLID 2021, 6-9)
2. Steps In Writing an Essay (EUCLID 2021, 10-14)
3. American Vs British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. The Importance of a Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 40-42)

BASICS OF ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I start writing this essay with many emotions, feelings, and anxiety. This Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) feels like a dream come true. I am taking my time to understand the Program and the course requirements. The information is too much, which makes me nervous. Last week I registered myself to the CMS and LMS portal. In the beginning, I wanted to determine what differentiates the two. After going through the orientation document, I got hold of what the two are. I read the period 1-course pack and the associated videos. They are an excellent first step; as writing is an art, we must all excel as researchers. English is indeed a Universal language, but it is interesting to note that academic writing has rules we should follow. It is always helpful to brush your knowledge and keep updated with the latest understanding of the subject.

The ACA 401 D course pack is comprehensive and explains academic writing steps. It not only discusses broad topics but also highlights sometimes neglected aspects such as the use of punctuation, referencing styles, and Latin abbreviations.

The video on how to write a Response Paper was helpful when writing this. I was new to the use of Zotero and the Turabian style guide.

In this Response paper, I will talk about key points that stood out for me from the ACA 401 D course pack and the videos, Basics of Academic Essay, writing styles (UK vs. US), the importance of having a writing style guide, as well as Plagiarism.

2) BASICS OF ACADEMIC ESSAY

The first topic discussed in the course pack is essay writing and how to write it effectively. It was argued that an academic essay is primarily a focused piece of paper that uses evidence, analysis, and explanation to develop an idea or argument. As a student, we write many types of essays. The content and length of those depend on the level, field of study, and course requirements. The course pack discussed that the essays should be researched properly. Having a well-researched supporting argument will be very beneficial (EUCLID 2021, 8). Time spent on researching will give the best results. But, going through a lot of text will sometime be mind-boggling; therefore, it is necessary to organize those ideas.

An academic essay has three main parts introduction, a body, and a conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 10). It was interesting to know that writing essays in one go are not advisable. Giving it time and then reviewing it can make it help look better.

I noticed how vital punctuation is (EUCLID 2021, 15-20). They form an important basis for an academic essay. Their effective use adds clarity and precision. They emphasize or stop a writing piece. I understood that if not used correctly, they can change the entire meaning of the sentence.

As discussed in the course pack, the rule of thumb for writing a paper is worth mentioning (EUCLID 2021, 12). It was a meaningful discussion as sometimes we tend to get carried away by writing generalities. The authors of this course pack told us we should not do that. Also, the writing should be clear with a clear goal in mind. Another point that grabbed my attention was not plagiarizing or citing your work correctly. Plagiarizing is severe academic misconduct, and one should always be mindful of that.

3) STEPS IN WRITING AN ESSAY

Writing an academic essay follows logical steps. It usually starts with understanding the problem question/assignment topic. The second and most important step for me is researching the topic. It will form the basis of the academic essay. The writer should keep taking notes while reading about the subject (EUCLID 2021, 7-10).

The writing should be divided into an introduction, the main point, or the body of the text and should typically end in a conclusion.

The essay's main body should elaborate on the issues raised in the introduction and develop an argument that answers the question. It should consist of several self-

contained paragraphs, each of which makes a specific point and provides evidence to support the idea (Oxford University, n.d.).

4) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

English is not my first language, but we have studied English in school since Day 1, right in Kindergarten. So we use British English in my country. I was aware of the few differences between British and American English, but the course pack gives a detailed insight into those. It was interesting to note why American English is the dominant or widely used worldwide. And for the first time, I realized why having a standard way of writing is crucial, especially in academic essays. I decided that I would follow US English style.

I tried to group these differences, 1) pronunciations, 2) Vocabulary and 3) spellings.

There are of course many other differences in the usage of quotation marks, commas, and periods (EUCLID 2021, 31).

5) THE IMPORTANCE OF A STYLE GUIDE

"A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent" (EUCLID 2021, 41).

A writing style guide is crucial as it gives consistency and cohesiveness and reflects a particular writing brand. Having multiple authors involved ensures that each is following the same writing style. Typically the writing style is a template document that sets standards for writing, punctuation, grammar, formatting, and designing for a particular company, University, or brand.

I have been following APA (American Psychological Association) writing style guide, which many Universities recommend. At my workplace, I also use APA. It has some advantages, as it makes the writing clear, easily readable, and has a familiar structure that can be followed. This topic is debated in the course pack for ACA 401 D. There should be a single writing style for the academic community. This issue can be pretty controversial. As I mentioned above, the EUCLID style guide Turabian is new to me.

6) PLAGIARISM

In the course pack, Plagiarism is defined as “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2021, 34).

The Oxford dictionary defines Plagiarism as "Presenting someone else's work or ideas as your own, with or without their consent, by incorporating it into your work without full acknowledgment."

It is essential to give the source of the reference material as it is ethical misconduct to portray someone else's work as yours. It is also wrong because if you steal someone else's work, you have not learned, which undermines individual academic achievement. Consequences can be severe and detrimental to the researcher. One loses credibility.

I learned that there are two types of citations 1) in text and 2,) a List of works cited. There are rules on how to cite both in the text and the lists of references. These will be beneficial for me in the future of my study program.

The author can give due credit when using any form of borrowed text, i. e., paragraphs, quotations, and paraphrases.

7) CONCLUSION

To conclude I would say that this course pack is a good start for what lies ahead. It also makes me realize that learning is unending.

To write a good and meaningful academic writing piece we need to be clear, well-researched, and organized. The writer should be mindful of the structure of the essay. It is also important to use a consistent writing style as well as a writing variant. The essays should be authenticated without any generalizations and/or sweeping statements. This brings me to the last point of citing the work or in other words avoiding plagiarism.

REFERENCES

Cleenwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA- 401/ACA-401D Coursepack: period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Oxford University, n.d. “*Essay and dissertation writing skills*” Accessed November 13, 2022. <https://www.ox.ac.uk/students/academic/guidance/skills/essay>

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D
Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.